

AACHEN UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCES

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

The basis for policies on gender-based violence (GBV) at German universities is the General Equal Treatment Act (AGG) issued in 2006. It defines forms of discrimination, explicitly including sexual harassment, and obliges higher education institutions (HEIs) to establish a complaints unit for any discrimination-related issues. However, the AGG only includes employees, not students. In addition to national legislation, HEIs have to comply with regional laws and can create their own regulations. At present, there are over 400 HEIs in Germany, and there is no systematic data available on how many have developed regulations on GBV (Kocher & Porsche 2015). According to a survey conducted among HEIs, 54% of participating HEIs had established a complaints unit for cases of discrimination according to the AGG by 2016 (Antidiskriminierungsstelle des Bundes 2020).

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

The process of creating policy around GBV is just starting to gain traction at FHA. So far, only one general policy document exists that mentions GBV: 'The Operating Agreement on Social Behaviour in the Workplace'. Although there is a Gender Equality Plan in place, the current version does not include issues related to GBV. Several regulations, among which are a code of conduct, a new Gender Equality Plan (2022-2026), antidiscrimination guidelines, a prevention concept, and a communication strategy, are currently being developed with the help of an 'antidiscrimination working group'.

It was first developed to comply with the German AGG (General Equal Treatment Act) directive to introduce a Complaints Office. The recent 2019 update instructed the university management and the staff councils to appoint at least two contact persons for two years, one of whom at the Jülich campus. The policy document is divided into 12 paragraphs: scope, work climate, principles of application, official right of complaint, steps of dealing with complaints, composition of the official complaint unit for social behaviour at the workplace, official contact persons – fairness officers, external fairness officers, sensitisation and qualification, sanctions, confidentiality, and date of coming into force, period of validity. Definitions are provided in an appendix.

URL

The document is not available online.

Entry into force: This document was first introduced in September 2013 and was last revised in May 2019.

TRAINING

At the time of this report, only the Equal Opportunities Commission had been trained on issues of sexual harassment in the institution. Training courses are offered to improve social behaviour and to prevent and avoid harassment. The staff councils shall be involved in the conception of the training and the selection of the training providers.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

Not specified in the institutional fieldwork report.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The current agreement addresses **one** form of gender-based violence: sexual harassment.

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

7Ps covered: The policy addresses the following **5Ps**: prevention, protection, prosecution, provision of services, and policy.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Target groups

The policy addresses two target groups: academic and non-academic staff.

Intersectionality addressed

No.

Specific vulnerable groups

The policy addresses one group particularly vulnerable to GBV: staff with temporary contracts

Bystanders addressed: Yes. The role of bystanders is addressed in the complaint procedure, as witnesses of the affected persons' behaviour. The document reads:

'5.4.3 When analysing the actual situation, attention should be paid, for example, to how affected members of the Aachen University of Applied Sciences behave during everyday work, also in the eyes of other colleagues.'

- Has inhumane behaviour occurred?
- Is the work being distributed properly? (If cooperation is necessary)
- Is the work that needs to be done being done correctly?
- Do the counterparts talk to each other?
- What is the tone of communication?

Are there any complaints? If so, from whom and in what way? etc.'

Role of perpetrators addressed: Yes. The document addresses potential perpetrators by declaring that: 'all members of the Aachen University of Applied Sciences are requested not to interfere with the development of the personality of individuals. In particular, care must be taken that:

- no one is restricted in his or her possibility to express himself or herself or to talk to his or her colleagues and superiors, especially within the scope of his or her official duties,
- no one is curtailed in his or her ability to maintain social relationships,
- no one is damaged in his or her social reputation,
- no one is sexually harassed by words, gestures or actions,
- no one is discriminated against or humiliated by tasks assigned to them,
- no one is subjected to physical violence or working conditions that are harmful to health,
- no one is excluded by withholding information and thereby hindered in his or her work.'

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: No.

Monitoring: Yes. There is monitoring on the results of the institutional procedure. The document reads: 'As required, but after six months at the latest, the fairness officer shall hold a meeting with each of the former conflict parties. At this meeting, an appeal is made to the individual's sense of responsibility for the working atmosphere.' The mechanism is set out in the document, but, according to the opportunities officer, it is not used.

Evaluation: No. There is a provision in the document that reads: 'This agreement will be evaluated after one year for the first time on 1 September 2014 by the university management and the staff councils in order to incorporate experiences and improvements.' The responsible bodies are the university management and staff councils. However, no evaluation has yet been conducted.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

Yes. The policy sets out a step-by-step procedure for reporting and investigating cases of violence among staff.

The policy defines: who to contact, how to report, the description of the investigation, a time frame, responsible persons/units, outcomes and sanctions.

Contact persons: They are alternatively: supervisors, staff council members, the equal opportunity representative, the representative for the severely disabled, the internal fairness officer. These persons have an advisory function and may file a complaint with the consent of the person concerned.

How to report: University members who raise a complaint may first request a discussion with the opponent of the conflict under the neutral direction of a fairness officer. Upon request, the staff

councils shall be consulted. The complainant has the right to have this discussion within two weeks of the complaint. If this discussion does not result in a satisfactory resolution of the conflict and voluntary agreement, a mediation meeting must be held within the next two weeks. A fairness officer shall be appointed as a mediator. The next higher-level supervisor of the conflicting parties shall be included in this discussion. At the request of the complainant, the staff councils may become involved. If the two parties to the conflict fail to reach an agreement, or if the original grievance which gave rise to the complaint continues to exist, the matter shall be brought before the official grievance committee within the next two weeks. After hearing both sides, it shall make a binding recommendation to the head of the department. The complaints office records the process and determines who will assume responsibility for the follow-up and prepare the analysis of the current situation. In this first discussion it is important that the participants in the discussion show understanding for the suffering of the members of the Aachen University of Applied Sciences and their psychological distress and take their statements seriously. It is explained to the affected parties, without condemnation of one or the other, that it is expected that industrial peace, which is acceptable to all, must be established within two months, otherwise measures will have to be taken. Both parties will be asked to attend a seminar on social behaviour (conflict resolution) or employee management, if appropriate.

Description of the investigation procedure: If no positive change is apparent after two months, university management and staff councils shall hold a discussion on how to proceed. If the underlying conflict has escalated to such an extent that it is possible to discern harmful effects (psychological or physical) on the person affected, examples of the harmful behaviour (i.e. the type of misconduct and time it occurred) shall be recorded in writing by superiors (if not the person affected/accused).

Time frame: See how to report above.

Responsible persons/units: Superiors and the same persons as those listed under contact persons.

Outcomes: In discussions with employees, attention should be paid to whether and in what form continued employment is conceivable.

Sanctions: Not reported.

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

Acknowledgment: *this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researchers Monica Perez and Friederike Kressner in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

